

Scope of the 1+MG Initiative v1.1

Recommendation

The scope of the 1+MG is an important aspect as it defines a framework that can subsequently become decisive for the possible operations of the initiative. Before designing this framework, it is therefore recommended to first consider the envisaged scope. The guiding principle for the following suggestions is the vision as defined on page 5 in the Declaration of Cooperation.

Scope of purposes

Access to the jointly established genomic cohort is to be limited to purposes supporting the goals defined in the Declaration, namely to “*provide cross-border, data-driven health and care solutions to benefit citizens of the Union*”.

These are:

- Research for a better understanding of diseases with the aim to ultimately promote prevention, diagnosis and treatment,
- Better healthcare provision for an individual patient, and
- Policy development with the aim to provide better healthcare and preventive measures to a collective of patients and citizens; these may include policy development e.g. for healthcare system planning, the implementation of precision medicine, health technology assessment, quality and safety monitoring and improvement of healthcare provision, medicinal products and medical devices.

Access should only be given through 1+MG for purposes that aim at genomic and personalised medicine and public health. It is equally desirable to specify the purposes for which data access will not be granted (e.g., law enforcement).

Scope of data users

The scope of users should be strictly limited to the professionals who need to have access to fulfil the above described purposes. This may include public and private researchers, healthcare professionals, public health professionals, quality and healthcare managers, and public authorities such as medicinal agencies and other policy makers. Where citizens become active agents in their own health journey as foreseen in the Declaration, they may pursue access to 1+MG data jointly with their practitioner as a team. Where individuals request access to their own genomic data, this should be provided by the institutions responsible for sequencing and collection.

A robust and streamlined access process with accreditation of users and authentication procedures, tailored with a suitable access governance for the different purposes of access will be essential. In addition, contractual obligations as well as other organisational and technical safeguards need to be in place to ensure the purpose limitation of the user access, and compliance with the data protection level of the GDPR, in particular where users from outside the European Union or European Economic Area are accepted (see below).

Scope of data providers

Data to be included in the 1+MG initiative for secondary use can come from a multitude of sources, including national and regional genome initiatives, research projects or from healthcare. Companies may be providers as well as individual citizens wanting to directly “donate” their data.

The recommendation is to not limit the inclusion of data sets based on the source, but rather to solely rest the acceptance of data on compliance with the inclusion criteria (e.g., quality; ethico-legal compliance) and the acceptance of the scope of data use in the 1+MG with the associated data governance and use conditions by the data provider.

Territorial scope

- Membership in the 1+MG

The signatories of this declaration invite all Member States of the European Union, the European Economic Area (EEA) and the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) [summarised in the following under EU/EEA] to join this cooperation. However, membership of countries in the 1+MG and participating in the joint genome cohort does not necessarily have to be limited to the EU/EEA. While the primary goal is to build a European resource, the 1+MG could in principle be open for all countries wishing to contribute to the same goals and that are ready to subscribe to the participation conditions and the ethico-legal framework of the initiative. Among other acknowledgements, where countries are not a member in the EU/EEA, they would have to guarantee an equivalent level of protection to personal data as in the EU and share ethical values. Where the territorial framework for the 1+MG membership does not have to be limited, the possible option for a wider scope may be advisable to remain flexible. Where data access is extended internationally, there will need to be appropriate legal mechanisms, safeguards, and transparency.

- Data users

Apart from the territorial scope of membership, it should be considered if only users located within 1+MG signatory states should be allowed to use the data or if also users independent of the 1+MG can request access. Here, the recommendation is that data use for healthcare and policy development for local or national health policies should be limited to users from the 1+MG signatory states, because these purposes benefit the local users only. Such local benefit should be the prerogative of members. This will be an incentive to join the initiative and provide a benefit in line with the data contributions made and the substantial investments for realising the infrastructure.

Where 1+MG data use aims at the improvement of global knowledge on genomic and personalised health such as in research or health technology assessment, access should be given to qualified and trustworthy users globally, because also the 1+MG members will benefit from new insights. However, where the stakeholders are not based in a 1+MG member state, stricter access and use conditions may be appropriate, such as limitations on possible operations on the platform, publication embargos, restricting uses to non-commercial purposes, or placing conditions on commercialization (e.g., joint IP rights) to ensure benefits are shared with Europeans.

Background

The following text provides further background to support the recommendations above.

Scope of purposes

The Declaration aims at creating a pan-European genome cohort for promoting biomedical and public health research and as a resource for enabling personalised medicine. However, a large-scale genomic collection could serve a multitude of purposes and it should be prevented that the original purpose may be infiltrated with additional purposes that were not agreed among the participating countries originally. A large-scale collection of genomes that

can trace back to the respective data subjects and that is combined with clinical data will attract a number of stakeholders. There are great concerns by data subjects that unauthorised access to and misuse of such data could lead to disadvantages, such as discrimination by private insurers or employers. Based on these concerns, several countries have even implemented that the use of genetic data for these purposes are prohibited. Correspondingly, a genome resource set up in the public interest of health should not serve such private purposes leading to discrimination. However, there are other, less clear-cut cases of secondary use which need to be decided upfront before the launch of the I+MG.

Law enforcement is increasingly building on genetic evidence and healthcare and research related genomic databases will have a different coverage of data subjects than forensic databases. It may happen that the police may want to have access to a transnational database to identify potential suspects based on DNA samples gathered at the scene of crime in a terrorist attack. A prominent example for the use of genomic data in law enforcement is the conviction of the assassin of the Swedish Minister for Foreign Affairs after access was given to the national biobank.

Another, not unlikely secondary use outside the scope of the Declaration is the identification of victims as often needed in a mass casualty event. Again in Sweden, a temporary law was passed to be able to quickly identify deceased victims of the 2004 tsunami in Thailand.

While such secondary uses may be justified in the public interest, these extended purposes are not in line with the original scope of I+MG, and may not be covered by the underlying consent. Adding additional purposes outside the original goal may erode trust, and undermine public acceptance of and willingness to share their genomic and health data.. A loss of trust in the data access governance, however, can subsequently not only lead to a decreased willingness to agree to secondary use of health data but can also affect healthcare itself. Where data from healthcare is included in databases for secondary use without perceived control, people may withhold information from their practitioners^[1] or fail to seek medical help in general^[2].

It is therefore strongly recommended to exclude explicitly any additional secondary use as an accepted scope of processing in the I+MG initiative and limit the use to the focus of the Declaration originally signed by the countries. Such limitation does not preclude the use of national datasets where it is permitted within national laws and complies with national ethical values. Instead of permitting direct cross-border law enforcement access for example, agencies can directly collaborate with their national counterparts. However, such data use would then take place independent of the I+MG and outside its operations. In particular, no data from other countries would be affected by such processing. Questions remain as to what safeguards the I+MG could adopt to enforce this purpose limitation, and what steps countries can take to prohibit misuse of data (e.g., genetic non-discrimination laws).

Scope of data users

The most determining factor for the scope of data users in the I+MG initiative is the definition of the purpose for data use. It is therefore recommended that approved users are defined by the necessity of their data access to achieve the ultimate aim of better prevention and healthcare. To achieve the purpose of a development of better understanding of underlying disease mechanisms for novel disease stratification and treatment strategy typically, access by public (or where applicable, private) researchers is required. For the actual development of innovative medicinal products, diagnostic devices and decision

support systems for personalised medicine, this may not be enough; researchers from pharmaceutical, biotech and IT companies may require access as well to fulfil the goal of translating information to knowledge to products and service for healthcare.

The same considerations as above are true for policy development applications, which will widen the group of potential users beyond researchers to policy makers and public health experts, public authorities such as medicinal agencies etc. The reason for giving access should always be based on a justified purpose that can realistically be achieved by the person requesting access and the methodologies proposed.

In the context of healthcare provision, the I+MG Healthcare Use Case Workshop demonstrated that users requesting access can come from an entire team around the patient from the treating physician to laboratory representatives. The authentication mechanisms need to foresee therefore a role based access management for the healthcare professionals. The Declaration also foresees that the I+MG initiative will have a citizen focus and lead to a more participatory approach to healthcare and a better understanding of the benefits of sharing genomics and health data. Such goals can be achieved where there is a team of the healthcare professional jointly with the patient. Only appropriately licensed, qualified, and authorized healthcare providers under professional secrecy with a clear mandate for a healthcare or public health benefit should be able to request access to ensure the purpose binding of the data use within the initiative. The qualifications, professional obligations and regulatory oversight structures for healthcare users - as well as whether this will be determined centrally or nationally - will be elaborated as part of the future deliverable to develop an access governance framework. Where citizens want to have access to their own genomic data, access should be provided by the institutions responsible for sequencing and collection.

The purpose driven principle of data access means that the data access governance is of central importance. Users should not be discriminated by their profession and/or their affiliation but admitted to the processing based on their role and relevance in achieving the respective purpose. The data access governance has therefore to foresee context and role based decision making criteria and the access request procedures and governance need to be tailored accordingly. The subsequent processing environments should also be designed to the respective use requirements to ensure both that the objective of the initiative can be reached and that data use will not compromise the integrity of the data or jeopardise the trust of the data subjects. Users will generally only be able to access data in secure and monitored computing environments hosted at national sites. The access governance framework will be elaborated in future outputs of the I+MG WG2 ELSI.

Scope of data providers

The I+MG is driven by the public sector. Correspondingly, the most likely sources of data for the I+MG are data from national genome initiatives as well as from healthcare where secondary use of data was implemented. Also, research projects that have consented the use of data for future use may be included. However, the focus on the public sector does not mean data from private stakeholders should be excluded. Such contributions could potentially be expected as part of public-private interactions. Even individual data subjects may want to contribute their data to the initiative as expression of a data altruism. This could e.g. be in the context of data generated in the healthcare, research or the private sector where these data are not foreseen for I+MG contribution by the data controller. The right to portability does allow the data subjects to ask for the transmission of their data to other recipients such as the I+MG.

Once again, the recommendation is not to limit the scope of the initiative a priori by categories but rather to focus on achieving the aim of the I+MG initiative. Data to be admitted to the I+MG collection should be qualified by their legal and functional interoperability rather than the source. Where the data offered can be integrated from a legal and ethical point of view, an inclusion should be considered. Such consideration then requires the review if the data comply with the quality requirements defined for I+MG, the coverage of the minimal dataset and defined metadata to make the data FAIR. The data providers will have to accept the conditions for data use within the I+MG, ranging from data access governance to rights in IP to the limitation in withdrawing data from the initiative. An “accreditation” procedure to verify the suitability of data for inclusion in the I+MG has to be established and a contractual framework is needed that allows the integration of data from different stakeholders.

For setting up the I+MG, a gradual process could be considered where not necessarily all possible data providers contribute from the very beginning. A step-wise procedure is possible as long as the organisational and legal framework of the initiative leaves the freedom of development for data contributions from all possible sources.

Territorial scope

The Declaration of Cooperation was signed by 13 EU Member States on the Digital Day in 2018 under the Bulgarian Presidency of the Council of the European Union. The aim is to improve the healthcare for the EU and to strengthen the EU scientific capabilities and industrial competitiveness in the field of genomic and personalised medicine. To realise these goals, the Declaration foresees secure cross-border processing of genomic and health data in the EU. While the Declaration has a strong focus on the EU, it is nevertheless worth considering if a wider territorial scope may be worth considering for its merits and downsides before tying up a legal framework.

- ***Membership in the I+MG***

Despite its focus on EU as main target, the Declaration invites all countries of the European Union, European Economic Area and the European Free Trade Association to join. That the concept of the I+MG is attractive in general is demonstrated by Norway signing the Declaration as the first country outside the EU.

In principle, there is no need to a priori exclude countries outside the invited scope of EEA/EFTA from a potential membership. The reasons acknowledged in the Declaration that a broad sharing of genomes will benefit the overall development of personalised medicine will apply similarly to a potentially widened scope of non-EU countries. The more countries contribute to the genomic cohort, the higher the impact and the scope of results that can be achieved. With a strong European focus, it is likely that the initiative is mostly appealing to European countries but once it becomes a successful model, it is quite possible that the scope of interest for membership will widen. Challenges may arise from the legal framework under which the I+MG is operating. The compliance with data protection standards as given by the GDPR will be one of the biggest hurdles. Membership would therefore be subject to suitable legal instruments and acknowledgements to solve the challenges but may not be excluded per se. It is therefore worthwhile to leave the scope of membership in the initiative flexible to be able to take on board valuable partners outside the EU/EEA/EFTA where there is a mutual interest and a compatibility of the ethico-legal framework.

- *Data users*

The territorial scope of data use in the I+MG initiative should be reviewed considering the intended outcome. The Declaration wants to build on genomic data sharing to improve research and ultimately healthcare in a vision for a genomics driven personalised medicine accessible to the European citizens. Genomic research is ultimately a global exercise and is less likely to succeed in a confined environment. In addition, the outcome of a better understanding of diseases and the development of new treatment approaches can benefit the European citizens independent of the country of origin of the user. As such, the extension of users to researchers beyond the signatory states is strongly recommended.

It should be considered though that different use conditions should be set up for users outside the I+MG member states. The adapted use conditions should once again reflect the objectives of the Declaration. With the improvement of personalised medicine in Europe and an increased European competitiveness, such use could be limited to pre-competitive research or, at minimum, knowledge generation only. It may also be considered that in case of innovation-driven purposes with commercialisation potential pursued by public or private researchers outside the I+MG, IP rights have to be shared with European partners or subject to licensing requirements favorable to European markets.

Similarly to research, also other purposes that aim at the generation of general knowledge benefitting public health in Europe such as health-technology assessment should be supported by the I+MG initiative beyond the range of the member countries.

In line with the aim of the Declaration to protect the privacy of the data donors, use conditions could furthermore include additional safeguards for the protection of data. Global use of data for biomedical research and public health purposes needs to be scrutinised carefully for a GDPR compliant implementation. Public health as an acknowledged reason of important public interest can provide the legitimation for I+MG to allow access by users outside the EEA. The technical approach of I+MG to bring compute to the data rather than allow downloading of data by the user will thereby be an essential safeguard to protect the data. Higher degrees of control of the processing may be exercised by the I+MG in such cases. The use of data could be limited to applications that have a negligible likelihood of compromising the privacy of the data subjects. The I+MG may also consider the introduction of a publication embargo to ensure integrity.

Contrary to research and knowledge generation purposes, the situation for the territorial scope is different where the benefit of the access remains local at the user's side. This is the case for access to pursue individual healthcare purposes, quality benchmarking, own policy development etc. There are several reasons to restrict this kind of access to the signatory states only. Looking beyond the EEA, the important reasons of public interest to base the access by third countries on would no longer apply in these cases. It is also important to consider that access for healthcare is more trust-based. Healthcare professionals will receive access based on their role and their agreement to terms of use. Subject-level data may be required in some cases of healthcare use or a direct contact to treating physicians of individual patients whose data was included in the I+MG. Such high-risk processing of personal data should only happen in a clearly defined community with agreed principles and thorough safeguards.

In addition, it needs to be considered that members of the I+MG are willing to make their data available in the I+MG. This requires substantial commitment and investment in terms of trust, logistics and infrastructure. Such contribution should thus be rewarded by being

able to have a higher benefit of data use. The limitation of local benefit to members of the initiative only will thus serve also as an incentive to participate in the 1+MG initiative and support the effort for a European genomic health and personalised medicine.

[1]Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology, *Big Data and Public Health*, July 2014,
[2] Princeton Survey Research Associates: Medical Privacy and Confidentiality Survey
(1999)

Change Log

Version	Author	Date	Description of Change
V1.0	ELSI WG2	Oct 2020	Initial Draft
V1.1	Adrian Thorogood	March 2021	Incorporated comments and edits from the October 2020 Signatories Meeting. Incorporated comments and edits from the Feb 2021 Scientific and Ethics Advisory Board meeting. Greater precision was added around the “scope of purposes”, being limited to only those relating to personalised medicine and public health.
V1.2	Adrian Thorogood	June 2021	Incorporated comments and edits from the NL delegation to 1+MG to improve the clarity; explanations were added on the need of additional safeguards in case of data use by entities outside the EEA, on scope of data users, the role of the background text as well as an emphasis that 1+MG also covers data use to foster prevention.